

Base Adducts of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Chelates with Some Schiff Bases

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Base adducts of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of *N,N'*-ethylene-bis(2-OH-5-Me aceto-phenone/propiofenone) are synthesised and characterised by elemental analyses, molar conductance, molecular weight, magnetic susceptibility, ir and uv spectra.

BASE adducts of complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with *N,N'*-ethylene-bis(2-OH-5-CH₃/Cl acetophenone/propiofenone)(H₂L) and bases (B) dipyritydyl/*o*-phenanthroline have been prepared and characterised. They analyse as ML₂B (B=dipy or *o*-phen).

The ligands were prepared as per literature^{1,2} by condensing the ketones, viz. 2-OH-5-CH₃/Cl aceto/propiofenone with ethylenediamine in alcohol for about 1 h. They were precipitated by pouring on ice. The precipitates were filtered, dried and recrystallised from chloroform.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: Equimolar quantities of nickel or cobaltous chloride (A.R. grade) in water were refluxed with the ligand in dioxane in presence of an acetate buffer (pH 6.5) for ~1 h. The orange-red precipitates of Ni^{II} or Co^{II} complexes with Schiff bases which separated on cooling were filtered. These complexes were dried in vacuum at room temperature and were then used as starting material for reacting with the two bidentate bases.

Dipyritydyl and *o*-phenanthroline adducts were prepared by refluxing a mixture of Co^{II} or Ni^{II} chelates prepared as above and dipy/*o*-phen in chloroform. Chloroform was removed under vacuum. The complexes were washed with carbon tetrachloride to remove excess metal Schiff base chelate and later with acetone to remove excess of dipy/*o*-phen. The base adducts being insoluble in both solvents, the adducts were recrystallised from chloroform in which they are fairly soluble in cold but much more in hot. The adducts were also soluble in DMF. The solubility in chloroform has been exploited for molecular weight determination by ebullioscopic method.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis (Table 1) done by standard methods³ showed that the complexes have

a ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 of M : L : B (M=Co/Ni; B=dipy/*o*-phen). The ebullioscopic determination of molecular weights of all the complexes in chloroform showed that they were monomeric. Thus, the Schiff bases seem to behave as tetradentate dibasic ligands as is known⁴⁻¹⁰. The bidentate bases make the metal ions six-coordinate and the bases must be occupying *cis* position. The low conductivity of all the complexes in chloroform confirms the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The room temperature magnetic moments (Table 1) by the Gouy method (Hg[Co(SCN)₄]) as calibrant corrected for diamagnetism) of all the Co^{II} complexes are 4.7-5.2 B.M. suggesting an octahedral geometry. Such magnetic moments for Co^{II} complexes are known¹¹ with a ⁴T_{1g}(F) ground state in an O_h symmetry. Here the symmetry is much lower. The room temperature magnetic moment of all the Ni^{II} complexes are found to be in the range of 2.9-3.3 B.M. Such magnetic moments of Ni^{II} complexes⁶ suggest an octahedral symmetry with a ³A_{2g} ground state on an idealised O_h basis.

The ir spectra of all the adducts showed the absence of O-H stretching band at ~3600 cm⁻¹ (observed in the ligands) suggesting its deprotonation for the purpose of complex formation. This is confirmed by M-O stretching band¹² at ~440 cm⁻¹. A band at ~512 cm⁻¹ is considered to be due to M-N bonds¹³. The band at 1630 cm⁻¹ found in the ligands is found to have shifted to 1590-1610 cm⁻¹ in these complexes, thereby suggesting the C=N group¹⁴ participation in coordination to the metal ion. The band found at 260-300 cm⁻¹ may be due to ν_{M-N} of the dipy/*o*-phen.

The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes in chloroform exhibit bands around 400 and 505 nm which are also present in all the ligands. Three more weak bands are also observed around 750 (ε=13.5), 710 (ε=14.5) and 530 nm (ε=340). These bands may be assigned^{9,15,17} to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P), respectively.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes in chloroform exhibit the intra-ligand bands around

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF Ni^{II} AND Co^{II} COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Complex	Mol. wt.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Conductivity Ω cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ _{eff} B.M.
			Ni/Co	Cl	N		
1.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-aceto)Ni ^{II} dipy	545.5 (536.71)	10.95 (10.94)	—	10.41 (10.43)	9	3.1
2.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-propio)Ni ^{II} dipy	558.7 (564.71)	10.89 (10.4)	—	9.87 (9.91)	8.3	3.3
3.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-aceto)Ni ^{II} dipy	585.3 (577.71)	10.2 (10.16)	12.28 (12.29)	9.67 (9.69)	10	3.1
4.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-propio)Ni ^{II} dipy	593.5 (605.71)	9.69 (9.7)	11.70 (11.72)	9.30 (9.24)	12	3.0
5.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-aceto)Ni ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	550.4 (560.71)	10.48 (10.47)	—	9.96 (9.98)	7.2	3.0
6.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-propio)Ni ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	573.5 (588.71)	9.95 (9.97)	—	9.52 (9.50)	8	3.2
7.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-aceto)Ni ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	610.5 (601.71)	9.77 (9.75)	11.9 (11.7)	9.25 (9.30)	7.5	2.9
8.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-propio)Ni ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	620.2 (629.71)	9.30 (9.32)	11.3 (11.27)	8.91 (8.89)	7.3	3.1
9.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-aceto)Co ^{II} dipy	523.4 (536.9)	10.6 (10.9)	—	10.41 (10.43)	11	4.7
10.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-propio)Co ^{II} dipy	552.9 (564.9)	10.3 (10.4)	—	9.93 (9.91)	10.5	4.9
11.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-aceto)Co ^{II} dipy	572.5 (577.9)	9.9 (10.1)	12.1 (12.3)	9.64 (9.69)	9.2	5.1
12.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-propio)Co ^{II} dipy	600.5 (605.9)	9.5 (9.7)	11.5 (11.7)	9.21 (9.24)	8.5	4.8
13.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-aceto)Co ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	570.5 (560.9)	10.3 (10.5)	—	9.96 (9.98)	10.5	4.9
14.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Me-propio)Co ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	572.2 (588.9)	10.2 (10.0)	—	9.53 (9.50)	7.5	4.8
15.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-aceto)Co ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	611.3 (601.9)	9.9 (10.1)	11.4 (11.8)	9.27 (9.30)	9.0	5.1
16.	<i>N,N'</i> -ethylene-bis (2-OH-5-Cl-propio)Co ^{II} <i>o</i> -phen	635.6 (629.9)	9.73 (9.7)	11.4 (11.7)	8.91 (8.89)	10.2	5.0

aceto = Acetophenone ; propio = propiophenone ; dipy = dipyridine , *o*-phen = *o*-phenanthroline.

400 and 505 nm. Two other bands are observed at 550 (ε = 640) and 490 nm (ε = 1600). The two bands may be assigned^{18,19} to ⁴T_{1g}(F) transition splitting being due to the fact that all the six near-neighbours are not the same so that the actual molecular symmetry is much lower.

The structure of the base adducts could be represented as,

where M = Co/Ni

The point of interest is that one of the M—O bonds in the square planar Schiff base complex of the metal is broken to make room for the base-ligands whose two nitrogens necessarily occupy *cis* positions.

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